

Effect of sewage sludge on carbamate pesticides adsorption in soils of Aligarh district

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Adsorption of three carbamate pesticides (I, II, III) used as nematicide and herbicides has been determined from solutions of six soil samples of Aligarh District at three different temperatures. On all the six soil samples the adsorption of pesticides is in the order III > I > II. The adsorption isotherms are of L-type. The adsorptivity of the soils is in the order, soil No. 1 > 2 > 3 > 4 > 5 > 6. The enthalpy change (ΔH°) reveals that the process is exothermic and there was an entropy loss in adsorption. Various studies, viz. Freundlich adsorption isotherms, thermodynamic parameters, IR and others reveal the existence of protonation or coordination (or both) between soils and oxygen of >C=O group of the pesticides. The results of this work also indicate that organic matter applied to soils as sewage sludge is capable in increasing the extent of adsorption to soil.

Ground application is the primary source of disposing off municipal and industrial sludge. These sludge contains heavy metals and organic matter, but these differ considerably in terms of kind and amount of heavy metals present¹. On being added to soil the sludge may affects significantly, not only the total content but also the chemical composition, properties and more specifically the function and reactivity of native organic matter of soil, as humic acid fraction can incorporate proteinaceous and S-containing materials originated from the sludge².

Pesticides applied to soils amended with sewage sludge will thus, interact with a complex mixture of sewage sludge and native organic matter which is expected to affect both quantitative and mechanistic aspect of adsorption phenomenon³. The behaviour of pesticidal residues depends strongly on the extent to which they are retained in soils, which depends on adsorption and desorption properties of soil. Adsorption desorption depends on temperature, soil composition

and soil pH⁴⁻⁶. Carbamate pesticides, oxamyl [(methyl-2(dimethylamine)-N[(methylamino)carbonyloxy]-2-oxoethanimidothioate (CH₃)₂NCO(SCH₃)=NOCONHCH₃ (I); S-ethyl-N[methyl(carbamoyloxy)thioacetimidate CH₃NHCON=C(CH₃)(SC₂H₅) (II) and N-phenyl-(ethylcarbamoyl)propyl carbamate C₆H₅NHCOOCH(CH₃)CONHC₃H₇ (III), are nonionic pesticides, best suited for effective control of nematodes and herbs.

The purpose of the present study is to determine the extent and mechanism of adsorption of three carbamate pesticides on soils of Aligarh District (amended as well as non-amended with sewage-sludge), and also calculate thermodynamic parameters of adsorption using Biggar and Cheung model.

Results and discussion

Sorption : The physiochemical properties of the soils are given in Table 1. Freundlich adsorption equation was

Table 1. Important physicochemical properties of soils

Sample no.	Place	Taxonomical name	Silt %	Clay %	pH (1 : 2.5)	Organic C%	CaCO ₃ %	CEC (Cmol (P ⁺) kg ⁻¹)	Surface area m ² g ⁻¹	Major clay minerals
1.	Hathras	Alluvial Typic Ustochrept	38.8	16.2	7.8	0.88	6.3	12.8	38.6	I
2.	Sikandra Rao	Aridisol Typic Arigids	52.0	14.0	8.8	0.72	7.6	11.6	36.2	I
3.	Datawali	Aridisol Typic Orthids	37.5	12.0	7.4	0.63	5.8	10.8	30.1	M, I
4.	Khair	Aridisol Typic Orthids	44.9	13.6	7.6	0.56	6.6	10.3	27.2	I
5.	Atrauli	Calciorthents	24.9	9.8	8.3	0.44	8.8	9.9	32.1	I, K
6.	Bank of Yamuna Tappal	Calciorthents	27.1	8.5	8.1	0.48	9.0	8.6	25.6	I, K

I = Illite, M = montmorillonite, K = kaolinite.

Table 2. Freundlich adsorption isotherm constants of three carbamate pesticides (I, II, III) adsorption at 25, 35 and 45° on different soils of Aligarh district

Pesticide	Soils no.																	
	1			2			3			4			5			6		
	25°	35°	45°	25°	35°	45°	25°	35°	45°	25°	35°	45°	25°	35°	45°	25°	35°	45°
I $K_{\pm s}$	68.4 (1.6)	63.1 (1.8)	60.0 (1.6)	64.5 (1.5)	62.0 (1.6)	59.9 (1.6)	62.1 (1.4)	60.0 (1.5)	58.2 (1.5)	60.1 (1.3)	58.3 (1.5)	55.8 (1.4)	57.7 (1.6)	55.0 (1.1)	53.1 (1.4)	54.6 (1.2)	52.1 (1.1)	50.6 (1.3)
I $1/n_{\pm s}$	0.940 (0.01)	0.910 (0.01)	0.885 (0.005)	0.920 (0.01)	0.900 (0.005)	0.865 (0.005)	0.895 (0.01)	0.870 (0.01)	0.850 (0.01)	0.865 (0.005)	0.840 (0.005)	0.820 (0.01)	0.845 (0.01)	0.820 (0.005)	0.800 (0.005)	0.815 (0.01)	0.790 (0.005)	0.760 (0.005)
II $K_{\pm s}$	62.4 (1.9)	60.2 (1.6)	58.3 (1.7)	60.0 (1.7)	57.9 (1.5)	55.1 (1.4)	57.1 (1.5)	54.7 (1.6)	52.1 (1.5)	53.6 (1.3)	51.0 (1.4)	49.0 (1.4)	50.8 (1.5)	47.7 (1.1)	45.0 (1.3)	47.1 (1.2)	44.8 (1.4)	42.8 (1.3)
II $1/n_{\pm s}$	0.880 (0.02)	0.855 (0.01)	0.830 (0.005)	0.850 (0.01)	0.835 (0.005)	0.810 (0.01)	0.830 (0.001)	0.800 (0.001)	0.785 (0.005)	0.795 (0.01)	0.770 (0.005)	0.745 (0.01)	0.765 (0.01)	0.750 (0.005)	0.720 (0.01)	0.735 (0.005)	0.710 (0.01)	0.685 (0.005)
III $K_{\pm s}$	78.5 (2.4)	72.4 (2.0)	68.8 (2.1)	73.6 (2.5)	68.8 (2.3)	65.9 (2.4)	69.9 (2.0)	66.1 (2.1)	63.6 (1.9)	65.5 (2.0)	62.8 (1.8)	59.7 (1.7)	63.1 (1.7)	60.7 (1.8)	57.7 (1.6)	59.6 (1.7)	56.2 (1.5)	53.8 (1.4)
III $1/n_{\pm s}$	0.965 (0.01)	0.930 (0.01)	0.900 (0.01)	0.950 (0.01)	0.910 (0.01)	0.880 (0.01)	0.930 (0.01)	0.895 (0.01)	0.870 (0.05)	0.900 (0.005)	0.870 (0.01)	0.845 (0.01)	0.880 (0.005)	0.850 (0.01)	0.815 (0.005)	0.845 (0.005)	0.815 (0.01)	0.775 (0.005)

±The values in parentheses show standard error of estimate.

used to describe the three carbamate pesticides' adsorption on soil. The linear form of this equation is, $\log C = \log K + 1/n \log C_e$, where C is the amount (mg/g) of pesticide adsorbed, C_e is the equilibrium concentration in solution (mg/ml) and K and $1/n$ are constants. K is the amount adsorbed for unit equilibrium concentration of pesticide and $1/n$ reflects the curvature in the isotherm and may be taken to represent the energy distribution of sorption sites. The values are given in Table 2.

The values of $1/n$, during adsorption of pesticides at three different temperatures for all the six soils were found less than unity indicating a convex or L type of isotherm as defined by Giles *et al.*^{7,8} (Table 2). This kind of isotherm may arise due to minimum competition of solvent for sites on the adsorbing surface. The slope of the isotherm steadily decreases with rise in solute concentration, since vacant sites become less accessible due to progressive covering of the surface. Results of this type have been reported elsewhere⁹. The adsorption of carbamate pesticides is in the order, pesticide III > I > II (Table 2). Adsorption of all the three carbamate pesticides follows the order (Table 2) soil no. 1 > 2 > 3 > 4 > 5 > 6. The above inferences also supported by the values of $1/n$ and K .

Effect of organic matter: A positive correlation between soil organic-matter content and adsorption of all the three pesticides was observed. The data indicated that adsorption of pesticides increased with the increase in organic matter content of soils, denoting that organic matter is the primary sorbent for these pesticides¹⁰. These inferences were supported by increase in adsorption with the addition of

sewage/sludge as sewage/sludge contains organic matter.

Effect of clay content: The sorption of pesticides by soils was influenced appreciably by the % of clay content ($r = 0.91-0.93$). Cox *et al.*¹¹ found a contribution of the surfaces of mineral components of the soil clay to sorption. The results indicate that besides organic matter % of clay content influences the sorption of pesticides on soils.

Effect of soil pH: Besides organic matter and % of clay content, soil pH is also a important factor governing the sorption of pesticides¹². Experiments were performed with soil no. 1 to study the effect of soil pH on the sorption of pesticides at pH 4.5, 5.5, 6.5, 7.0, 7.5, 8.5, 9.5 and 10 (adjusted by 0.01 M HCl or 0.01 M NaOH). The adsorption of pesticides increased with pH upto 6.0 (pesticide III), 6.5 (pesticide II) and 7.0 (pesticide I) and thereafter decreased, which is near about pK values of pesticides. As soils are alkaline in nature there is no appreciable effect of soil pH on adsorption of pesticides.

Effect of temperature: An increase in temperature from 25° to 45° results in a decrease of adsorption of all the three pesticides, the effect is maximum in pesticide II followed by III and I. The decrease in adsorption may be attributed to two factors: (i) a change in the energy of adsorption or weakening (or both) of van der Waal's forces of attraction between the pesticide and soil surface¹³ causing a decrease in physical adsorption¹⁴; and (ii) a change in solubility of pesticides with a change in temperature. Similar results have also been reported by Burcher and Bergstrom¹⁵, Sanchez-Martin *et al.*¹⁶.

Effect of sewage sludge: The adsorption of pesticides

Table 4. Thermodynamic parameters for three carbamate pesticides adsorption on six different soils of Aligarh district at 25, 35 and 45°

Pesticide	Soil sample	Equilibrium constant			ΔG° kJ mol ⁻¹			ΔH°	ΔS°
		25°	35°	45°	25°	35°	45°	kJ mol ⁻¹	J mol ⁻¹ dg ⁻¹
I	1	256.6	206.3	161.6	-13.74	-13.65	-13.50	-16.72 ± 0.22	-10.13 ± 0.12
	2	239.9	194.3	150.3	-13.58	-13.49	-13.36	-16.64 ± 0.22	-10.24 ± 0.23
	3	228.8	176.1	134.5	-13.46	-13.24	-13.04	-20.52 ± 0.32	-23.55 ± 0.32
	4	212.1	163.1	124.1	-13.27	-13.04	-12.79	-20.24 ± 0.13	-23.02 ± 0.40
	5	190.4	148.4	116.3	-13.00	-12.80	-12.62	-19.04 ± 0.12	-20.14 ± 0.23
	6	172.6	138.5	110.5	-12.75	-12.63	-12.51	-16.74 ± 0.13	-13.42 ± 0.22
II	1	206.1	161.5	127.5	-13.20	-13.02	-12.82	-18.69 ± 0.13	-19.10 ± 0.12
	2	200.1	148.2	116.2	-13.13	-12.86	-12.60	-21.81 ± 0.12	-29.16 ± 0.52
	3	182.2	140.1	109.6	-12.90	-12.65	-12.42	-20.23 ± 0.22	-24.62 ± 0.36
	4	171.5	131.6	103.2	-12.75	-12.50	-12.28	-19.20 ± 0.18	-25.17 ± 0.32
	5	166.5	126.1	97.8	-12.67	-12.39	-12.12	-21.49 ± 0.30	-29.63 ± 0.44
	6	159.8	118.2	90.1	-12.57	-12.24	-11.90	-22.66 ± 0.15	-33.81 ± 0.56
III	1	274.1	213.1	168.8	-13.91	-13.73	-13.56	-19.01 ± 0.16	-20.47 ± 0.24
	2	254.1	202.7	160.7	-13.72	-13.60	-13.47	-17.56 ± 0.24	-10.87 ± 0.16
	3	239.2	187.1	150.1	-13.57	-13.40	-13.25	-17.68 ± 0.26	-13.79 ± 0.20
	4	222.6	175.2	130.2	-13.36	-13.12	-12.87	-21.10 ± 0.10	-25.64 ± 0.16
	5	200.4	160.6	124.2	-13.17	-13.00	-12.83	-17.06 ± 0.13	-17.05 ± 0.12
	6	187.5	151.4	120.4	-12.97	-12.80	-12.67	-17.00 ± 0.42	-13.52 ± 0.15

± The values show the standard error or estimation.

Table 5. Thermodynamic parameters for three carbamate pesticides adsorption on six different soils in presence of sewage sludge at 25°

Soil sample	Pesticide I						Pesticide II						Pesticide III					
	K_o			ΔG°			K_o			ΔG°			K_o			ΔG_o		
	Amount of sewage sludge (g) added per 100 g soil																	
	0	1	2	0	1	2	0	1	2	0	1	2	0	1	2	0	1	2
1	256.6	266.9	278.4	-13.74	-13.84	-13.95	206.1	211.2	222.2	-13.20	-13.26	-13.39	274.1	280.6	290.3	-13.91	-13.97	-14.05
2	239.9	248.2	263.4	-13.58	-13.66	-13.81	200.1	208.6	214.2	-13.13	-13.23	-13.30	254.1	263.6	281.2	-13.72	-13.81	-13.97
3	228.8	238.1	253.1	-13.46	-13.56	-13.71	182.2	198.6	209.2	-12.90	-13.11	-13.24	239.2	248.3	260.0	-13.57	-13.66	-13.78
4	212.1	228.3	240.1	-13.27	-13.46	-13.58	171.5	178.5	194.5	-12.75	-12.85	-13.00	222.6	238.2	251.1	-13.36	-13.56	-13.69
5	190.4	200.0	206.2	-13.00	-13.13	-13.21	166.5	176.2	186.2	-12.67	-12.81	-12.91	200.4	207.4	224.1	-13.17	-13.22	-13.41
6	172.6	183.1	194.1	-12.75	-12.91	-13.05	159.8	166.6	175.2	-12.57	-12.68	-12.80	187.5	198.2	218.7	-12.97	-13.11	-13.35

The data of thermodynamic parameters are given in Table 4.

The values of K_o (Table 4) have been found to be higher than unity for all the three carbamate pesticides indicating that pesticide has a high preference for soil surface, and they decrease in the order soil no. 1 > 2 > 3 > 4 > 5 > 6, confirming the earlier deductions regarding the order of adsorption. The values of K_o decreases as the temperature rises. The values of K_o increased in presence of sewage sludge (Table 5) suggesting that in presence of sewage-sludge, more of the pesticides are adsorbed.

The values of ΔG° were negative at all three temperatures and increased with rise in temperature, pointing towards the spontaneity of the reaction with a greater affinity (for pesticide) of soil. From the values of ΔG° our earlier deductions concerning the affinity of pesticides for the different soils at the experimental temperature stood confirmed. The values of ΔG° (Table 5) in presence of sewage/sludge,

were higher than in unamended soils, indicating higher affinity of the soils for pesticides in presence of sewage/sludge than in unamended soils.

The negative values of overall adsorption heat (ΔH°) indicate the exothermic nature of reaction with a strong binding of pesticide molecule on the soil surface. The low values of ΔH° also show that the adsorption occurs through covalent bonding mechanism and/or hydrogen bonding²¹. The entropy change which was affected by volume of displaced water indicated that pesticide-soil complexes are stable; association, fixation or immobilization of the pesticide molecule as a result of adsorption through a water bridge resulted in the loss of degree of freedom of the pesticide molecule, producing negative entropy effects.

The above inferences indicate that the non-ionic neutral carbamate pesticides may be adsorbed because of coordination and/or protonation (or both)²²⁻²⁴, hydrogen

bonding, and dipole associations or van der Waal's forces as follows.

The results suggest that adsorption of pesticide III was maximum as more sites are available for bond formation followed by pesticide I and II.

An examination of IR spectra show that the bands at 1670 (C=O), 1690 (C=N) and 1380 (C-N) cm⁻¹ in pesticide I, were shifted to 1645, 1705, 1390; 1650, 1710, 1390; 1650, 1710, 1395; 1660, 1710, 1395; 1655, 1700, 1390 and 1660, 1700, 1390 cm⁻¹ for soil nos. 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 respectively. The shift in presence of sewage sludge was from 1670 to 1640, 1690 to 1705 and 1380 to 1400 cm⁻¹. These shifts indicate the coordination and/or protonation (or both) with carbonyl oxygen with shifting of double bond towards nitrogen²⁵. The shift of band for pesticide II were from 1665 to 1650 cm⁻¹; 1690 to 1705 and 1385 to 1400 cm⁻¹ and for pesticide III were from 1675 to 1640 (C=O stretching); and 1380 to 1410 cm⁻¹ (C-N) stretching vibration.

Experimental

Six surface soils (0–30 cm; 1 to 6) from different parts of Aligarh district were collected and sieved through 100 mesh sieve.

Adsorption experiments were conducted taking soil samples (10 g) in a large number of stoppered conical flasks adding varying amounts of standard carbamate solution (0–15 ml of 5000 µg ml⁻¹) and the volume to 250 ml with distilled water. The samples were then shaken for 30 h in a constant temperature water bath at 25, 35, and 45 ± 0.5°, and then centrifuged for 10 min at 1500 g. The supernatants were estimated at 435 nm as copper dithiocarbamate²⁶. The amount of pesticide adsorbed was obtained from the amount added minus left in the supernatants.

The influence of sewage sludge on adsorption was investigated at 25 ± 0.5° by taking 10 g soil samples equilibrated with 100 and 200 mg of sewage sludge. The amount of pesticides in supernatant was estimated as discussed earlier.

IR analyses of soils and their complex samples were performed as described elsewhere²⁷.

All the experiments were conducted in duplicate with suitable blanks.

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References

1. L. E. Sommers, D. W. Nelson and K. J. Yost, *J. Environ. Quality*, 1976, **5**, 303.
2. N. Sensi, T. M. Miano and G. Brunetti, "Humic like substances in organic amendments and effects on native soil humic substances: In Humic substances in terrestrial Ecosystems", ed. A. Piccolo, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1996, pp. 531-593.
3. N. Sensi, P. L. Cava and T. M. Miano, *J. Environ. Quality*, 1997, **26**, 264.
4. W. C. Koskinen, G. A. O'Connor and H. H. Cheng, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.*, 1979, **43**, 871.
5. W. C. Koskinen and H. H. Cheng, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.*, 1982, **46**, 256.
6. R. Calvet, *Environmental Health Perspectives*, 1989, **83**, 145.
7. C. H. Giles, T. H. MacEwan, S. N. Nakhwa and D. Smith, *J. Chem. Soc., Part 3*, 1960, 3973.
8. C. H. Giles, D. Smith and A. Huiston, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 1974, **47**, 755.
9. A. Moreale and R. Van Bladel, *Clays and Clay Miner.*, 1979, **14**, 1.
10. S. Mitra, P. C. Bhowmik and B. Xing, *Pest. Sci.*, 1999, **55**, 935.
11. L. Cox, W. C. Koskinen, R. Celis, P. Y. Yen, M. C. Hermosin and J. Cornejo, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.*, 1998, **62**, 911.
12. R. G. Lehman, J. R. Miller, D. D. Fontaine, D. A. Laskowski, J. H. Hunter and R. C. Cordes, *Weed Res.*, 1992, **34**, 564.
13. E. Barriuso, U. Baer and R. Calvet, *J. Environ. Qual.*, 1992, **21**, 359.
14. Th. Stutzmann and B. Siffert, *Clays and Clay Miner.*, 1977, **25**, 392.
15. J. Brucher and L. Bergstrom, *J. Environ. Quality*, 1997, **26**, 1327.
16. M. J. Sanchez-Martin, J. M. Gonzalez-Pozuelo and M. Sanchez-Camazano, *Weed Res.*, 1993, **33**, 479.

17. R. Celis, L. Cox, M. C. Hermosin and J. Cornejo, *J. Environ. Quality*, 1997, **26**, 472.
18. J. W. Biggar and M. W. Cheung, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. Proc.*, 1973, **37**, 863.
19. D. A. Skoog and D. M. West, "Fundamentals of Analytical Chemistry", 3rd. ed., ed. P. R. Holt, Rinehart and Winston, New York, 1976.
20. R. G. D. Steel and J. H. Torrie, "Principles and Procedure of Statistics : A Biometrical Approach", 2nd. ed., McGraw Hill Book Co., New York, 1980.
21. A. Moreale and R. Van Bladel, *Soil Sci.*, 1979, **127**, 1.
22. M. M. Mortland, "Reactions between Clays and Organic Compounds", U.S.-Japan Seminar on Clay Organic Complexes, Kyoti, 1971.
23. M. Frenkel, *Clays and Clay Miner.*, 1974, **22**, 435.
24. O. P. Bansal, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.*, 1993, **47**, 877.
25. J. D. Russel, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1965, **61**, 2284.
26. J. P. Singhal, S. U. Khan and O. P. Bansal, *J. Agric. Food Chem.*, 1977, **25**, 377.
27. J. P. Singhal, S. U. Khan and O. P. Bansal, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1978, **31**, 2151.